

Interaction of ibuprofen with β -cyclodextrins : Experimental and molecular modeling studies

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Abstract : The aim of this work was to study the interaction of β -cyclodextrin and its chemically modified varieties (hosts) with ibuprofen (guest). For this purpose the physicochemical characterization of host-guest binary systems were carried out by UV-Visible (UV-Vis), Fourier transform infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy and quantum mechanical semi empirical PM3 calculation. UV-Vis and FTIR studies revealed inclusion complex formation and PM3 calculations correlated with the experimental findings. The adsorption of ibuprofen in aqueous solutions onto β -cyclodextrin-bonded silica phase (CDS) was also investigated with the aim of an in-depth understanding of the host-guest interaction. The kinetic behaviour of ibuprofen adsorbed on CDS revealed that the rate-limiting step may be chemical adsorption, which confirmed that adsorption of ibuprofen takes place via inclusion complexation. Scanning electron micrographic (SEM) studies showed morphological differences in the unloaded adsorbent and the changes in the adsorbed CDS.

Keywords : β -Cyclodextrin, ibuprofen, inclusion complex, formation constant, PM3 calculation.

Introduction

Ibuprofen is one of the most effective and widely used non-steroidal analgesic and anti-inflammatory agents. Non-steroidal analgesic and anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs) are commonly used for pain relief and have consistently been shown to reduce the risk of cancers¹. Recently, new therapeutic properties of ibuprofen have been discovered². For example, ibuprofen protects neurons from glutamate toxicity *in vitro*³ and is active against certain strains of *Candida*^{4,5}.

The formulation of ibuprofen has been problematic because of its poor solubility and wettability in water⁶. Cyclodextrins (CDs) are known to form inclusion complexes with hydrophobic molecules, and it has been used in formulations to improve water solubility⁷. Cyclodextrin (CD) has been used in drug delivery applications because of its capability to form inclusion complexes with drug molecules. It has been further demonstrated that the β -cyclodextrin (β -CD) complex of ibuprofen is less irritating to mucous membranes relative to the free drug and that both the undesirable taste and smell of ibuprofen are

masked by CD-inclusion⁸. Fig. 1(a) shows the chemical structure of β -CD.

Host-guest complexation studies with CD are important for drug delivery systems^{9,10}. CD has been used as a complexing agent for chromatographic and capillary electrophoretic separations of ibuprofen^{11,12}. Drug-carrier interactions between ibuprofen and native or chemically modified β -CD in solution and in the solid state have also been described^{13,14}. Modified CD can exhibit very different properties compared to the native material, which can be used for improving the selectivity of enantiomers for separation, e.g. increased solubility, possibility for different secondary bonds, potential for the analysis of uncharged compounds, and different hydrophobicity of the cavity¹¹.

In this paper, the interaction of ibuprofen with β -CD/derivatives as well as polymer were studied by UV-Visible (UV-Vis), Fourier transform infrared (FTIR) and molecular modeling. The stability constant for inclusion complex formation was determined by UV-Vis spectroscopy. Adsorption properties of ibuprofen with β -CD

bonded to silica gel has also been investigated. Experimental methods along with the theoretical ones will facilitate better understanding of the complexation of ibuprofen as model drug with β -CD as well as its derivatives.

Experimental

Materials :

The ibuprofen used in this study was obtained from Sigma-Aldrich Chemicals Pvt. Ltd., USA. The molecular structure of ibuprofen is also shown in Fig. 1(b). The β -CD was obtained from HiMedia Laboratories Pvt. Ltd., Mumbai, India. Other β -CDs used in this work such as β -CD hydrate (β -CD-Hyd), 2-hydroxypropyl- β -CD (HP- β -CD) and β -CD-sulphated sodium salt (S- β -CD) were obtained from Sigma-Aldrich Chemicals Pvt. Ltd., USA. The silica gel (60–120 mesh size) was obtained from SRL Pvt. Ltd., Mumbai, India. Compound 3-glycidoxypropyltrimethoxysilane was also obtained from Sigma-Aldrich Chemicals Pvt. Ltd., USA. The other reagents used as components in buffers (sodium phosphate, sodium acetate, sodium carbonate and sodium chloride) were sup-

plied by Qualigens, India (Mumbai) and were of analytical grade.

UV-Vis spectroscopy :

The UV spectra were recorded with a Varian Cary 50 Bio UV-Vis spectrophotometer using quartz cells, between 200 and 400 nm. In the experiments with ibuprofen (guest) with CD and its derivatives (hosts), the concentration of the hosts were varied from 1×10^{-3} M to 12×10^{-3} M while the concentration of the guest was kept constant at 2×10^{-3} M. The mixtures were stirred at 25 °C at a speed of 280 rpm for 4 h and the supernatant was analysed by UV-Vis spectrophotometer.

Preparation of drug-cyclodextrin inclusion complexes :

The guest and the hosts were fully dissolved in phosphate buffer (pH 8) at a molar ratio 1 : 1 and then the two solutions were mixed and stirred at 25 °C for 4 h. Dried complexes were obtained by lyophilisation in a freeze dryer, where samples were frozen and kept at -49 °C for 6 h followed by drying at 0.002 mbar for 12 h. The powders obtained were stored in gas-tight bottles at -20 °C until further analysis.

Instrumental studies :

FTIR spectra were obtained by the KBr method (Perkin-Elmer, model Spectrum One). Morphological features of samples were obtained with a (Zeiss Sigma) Scanning Electron Microscope.

Preparation of β -CD bonded silica stationary phase (CDS) :

As CDs are highly soluble in water, they must be processed into a solid form before utilisation in adsorption technologies. CD containing polymers are useful materials for selective adsorption or the separation of organic compounds. Therefore, a polymer (i.e. CDS) was synthesised as reported in earlier work^{15,16} in which β -CD was bonded to silica particles.

CDS was prepared according to a previously reported procedure^{17,18}. Briefly, 1.145 g of β -CD was dissolved in 25–30 ml of dry dimethyl formamide (DMF), to which 0.1 g of metal sodium was added. The reaction was allowed to proceed with stirring at room temperature for approximately 30–40 min. After filtration, 0.45 ml of 3-glycidoxypropyltrimethoxysilane was added to the filtrate, which was allowed to react at 90 °C for 5 h. Then, 5.0 g

Fig. 1, Chemical structure of (a) β -CD and (b) ibuprofen.

of silica gel was added, and the mixture was allowed to react for 10 h at 80–100 °C. The CDS was filtered, and washed with DMF, methanol, doubly distilled water and acetone in sequence. Subsequently, the CDS was dried at 120 °C for 3 h, and kept in a desiccator before use.

Adsorption experiment :

Equilibrium isotherm was obtained by contacting 25 ml of aqueous ibuprofen solution with different amounts of CDS in a thermostated shaker bath controlled at 25 ± 0.5 °C at pH 8. The pH of the solutions were measured with a pH meter and maintained at pH 8 by using phosphate buffer reagents of appropriate dosages. The initial concentration of ibuprofen in the aqueous solution was varied between 5 and 10 mM. Preliminary runs showed that the adsorption equilibrium was achieved after 4–6 h of contact time. After attaining equilibrium, the aqueous phase was analysed for solute concentrations of the ibuprofen by a UV-Vis spectrophotometer (Varian Cary 50 Bio, Sweden) calibrated at the maximum absorbance wavelength (λ_{\max}) of the specific ibuprofen. For quantitative spectrophotometric analysis, standard graph was prepared at λ_{\max} 222 nm for ibuprofen.

Approximately 0.2 ml of the supernatant liquid was drawn with glass syringe and diluted with the buffer used for preparing the ibuprofen solution. The absorbance was measured in the spectrophotometer and concentrations were determined using the calibration graph. The UV-Vis analysis was performed in duplicate and the reproducibility was found to be $\pm 2\%$. The amount of ibuprofen per gram of CDS 'q' (mmol g^{-1}) was calculated as $q = V\Delta C/W$ where, ΔC is the change in solute concentration (mmol L^{-1}), V is the solution volume and W is the weight of adsorbent (g).

Molecular modeling studies :

The inclusion process involving guest and hosts was investigated by using the PM3 quantum mechanical semiempirical method. All theoretical calculations were performed using GAUSSIAN 09 software package¹⁹. For all the systems, a full geometry optimization was done at the PM3 level. Using standard bond lengths as the initial input, the carbon chains or rings in the guest molecule was vertically inserted into the cavity of the hosts along the middle axis from the large rim of hosts in CHEM 3D. Stabilization energy (ΔE) upon complexation between guest

and the hosts were calculated for the minimum energy structure according to eq. (1)²⁰ :

$$\Delta E = E_{\text{complex}} - (E_{\text{guest}} + E_{\text{host}}) \quad (1)$$

where E_{complex} , E_{guest} and E_{host} represent HF energies (heats of formation) of the complex, the free guest and the host, respectively.

Results and discussion

UV-Vis spectroscopic studies :

UV-Vis spectrophotometric studies of the interactions of guest with hosts enabled the determination of stability constants of inclusion complexes when their formation gave rise to appreciable spectral changes. The absorption spectrum of free ibuprofen in phosphate buffer showed two peaks at 222 nm and 262 nm (Fig. 2). The UV-Vis absorption spectra of ibuprofen upon addition of β -CD,

Fig. 2. UV absorption spectra of ibuprofen.

HP- β -CD, β -CD-Hyd and S- β -CD in aqueous solution at 298 K are shown in Figs. 3(a), (b), (c) and (d), respectively. The concentration of the guest was kept constant at 2×10^{-3} M and the concentrations of the hosts were varied from 1×10^{-3} to 12×10^{-3} M. Upon complexation, the absorption intensities increased regularly with increase in concentration, and the absorption spectra also had been changed in each case. No change in λ_{\max} was observed in case of complexes with β -CD and β -CD-Hyd, though absorptivity increased with concentration. The absorption maximum was slightly blue shifted with a gradual increase in absorbance in case of ibuprofen-HP-

Fig. 3. UV absorption spectra of ibuprofen in presence of (a) β -CD, (b) HP- β -CD, (c) β -CD-Hyd and (d) S- β -CD.

β -CD complex. For ibuprofen-S- β -CD, a significant blue shift was observed, and changes in absorption spectra were also significant as CD strongly affected the absorptivity of the guest, which indicated that among the studied hosts, S- β -CD was better complexing agent for ibuprofen.

During the spectral changes, the chromophore of the guest was transferred from an aqueous medium to the non-polar CD. These changes must be because of a perturbation of the electronic energy levels of the guest caused either by direct interaction with the CD, by the exclusion of solvating water molecules or by a combination of these two effects^{21,22}. The shifts towards lower wavelength in the spectra of the complexes may be attributable to the formation of hydrogen bonds.

Because hydrogen bonding lowers the energy of 'n' orbitals, a hypsochromic shift (blue shift) was observed²³. The shift was more pronounced in case of complexes with S- β -CD, which may be due to the greater affinity of sulphated oxygen towards hydrogen bonding²⁴.

Determination of formation constants of the inclusion complexes of hosts with guest :

The determination of formation constants (K) of the host to the guest was realized by UV-Vis spectroscopy titration experiments. The K values were calculated by applying least-squares fit to the plots of $([host].[guest])/\Delta A$ versus $([host] + [guest])$, according to the modified Benesi-Hildebrand eq. (2)^{25,26} :

$$\frac{[host][gust]}{\Delta A} = \frac{1}{K\Delta\epsilon} + \frac{1}{\Delta\epsilon} ([host] + [gust]) \quad (2)$$

where, $[gust]$ and $[host]$ are the equilibrium concentrations of guest and hosts, respectively. $\Delta\epsilon$ is the difference between the extinction coefficients of free and complexed guest. ΔA is the difference between the absorbances of free and complexed guest at the same wavelength.

Fig. 4 shows the plots of $([host].[gust])/\Delta A$ versus $([host] + [gust])$. The initial concentration of ibuprofen was kept at $2.0 \times 10^{-3} M$, while the concentrations of the

Fig. 4. Plot of $([host].[guest])/\Delta A$ versus $[host] + [guest]$.

hosts were in the range from 1 to $12 \times 10^{-3} M$. A linear least-squares fits to the plots. The K values of inclusion complexes of hosts with guest were determined from the slopes and intercepts of the linear plots based on the eq. (2). The calculated K values of the inclusion complexes are summarized in Table 1. For all the four inclusion systems, the dependencies were linear in the investigated concentration range, confirming that the stoichiometries of the inclusion complexes in solution were 1 : 1^{27,28}.

Table 1. Calculated K values of the complexes

Complex	K (M)	Correlation coefficient
Ibuprofen- β -CD	1.134	0.986
Ibuprofen-HP- β -CD	1.493	0.969
Ibuprofen- β -CD-Hyd	1.009	0.998
Ibuprofen-S- β -CD	4.455	0.964

For β -CD and derivatives, the changes in K values reflected the following order : S- β -CD > HP- β -CD > β -CD > β -CD-Hyd. The lowest K value for β -CD-Hyd system is attributable to the presence of water molecules inside its cavity hindering the entrance of the guest molecule. The greater complexing ability of HP- β -CD compared to β -CD might be due the restricted motion of the hydroxyl group on the HP- β -CD propyl moiety than the rim hydroxyls in β -CD²⁹. One important use of HP- β -CD is to include insoluble drugs forming water soluble complexes so that stable water solutions can be prepared without organic solvents furthermore³⁰.

FTIR spectroscopic studies :

FTIR is a useful technique to confirm the formation

of CD-drug inclusion complexes³¹. FTIR spectra of inclusion complexes prepared by the freeze drying method exhibited significant differences in the characteristic bands, which revealed bond formation during complexation. The FTIR spectrum of pure ibuprofen showed two important absorption bands : one at 2955 cm^{-1} and another sharp band at 1722 cm^{-1} corresponding to the O-H and C=O groups respectively, of acidic part of the ibuprofen molecule. All the four complexes prepared by freeze drying method showed significant changes in these band positions demonstrating complex formation. In addition, the reduction in intensity of the C=O band may have resulted from its restriction within the β -CD cavity and shifts of O-H absorption bands to higher frequency regions supported that complex formation had occurred between the hosts and guest. Increase in O-H frequency can be due to the weakening of the hydrogen bond in the heptameric host units³². The disappearance or shift of the C=O stretching was reported earlier^{13,32} as evidence for the inclusion of ibuprofen inside the CD cavity.

Adsorption study :

Ibuprofen (4-isobutyl-2-phenyl-propionic acid) was used as an adsorbate in this work. The adsorption isotherm of ibuprofen on CDS is shown Fig. 5, where C_e (mmol L^{-1}) is equilibrium liquid phase concentration and q_e is the amount of ibuprofen adsorbed at equilibrium

Fig. 5. Adsorption isotherm of ibuprofen on CDS at pH 8.

(mmol g^{-1}). The adsorption equilibria were interpreted from Langmuir and Freundlich isotherms. Table 2 shows the values of the isotherm parameters estimated by non-linear regression analysis. Although both the isotherm

Table 2. Parameter values for the isotherms of ibuprofen on CDS at pH 8 (at 25 °C)

Adsorbate	Langmuir model			Freundlich model		
	$q_e = K_L X_m C_e / (1 + K_L C_e)$			$q_e = K_f C_e^n$		
	K_L	X_m	R^2	K_f	n	R^2
Ibuprofen	6.398	1.173	0.917	6.873	4.173	0.891

where, K_L , X_m are the parameters of Langmuir model and K_f , n are the parameters of Freundlich model.

models provided very good R^2 values, the Langmuir model provided the most satisfactory representation of the data. The Langmuir model was found to be satisfactory for the adsorption of ibuprofen on activated carbons^{33,34}.

Fig. 6 shows the effect of inclusion adsorption time on the quantity of ibuprofen adsorbed on CDS with different initial concentrations in phosphate buffer, where q_t

Fig. 6. Effect of inclusion adsorption time on the quantity of ibuprofen adsorbed on CDS at different initial concentrations. (■) Represents initial concentration 5 mmol L⁻¹; (◆) Represents initial concentration of 10 mmol L⁻¹.

(mmol g⁻¹) is the quantity of ibuprofen adsorbed on CDS at time t (h). The quantities of ibuprofen adsorbed on CDS increased with inclusion adsorption time and reach equilibrium within 4–6 h. A pseudo-second order model³⁵ was applied to analyze the kinetics behaviour of ibuprofen

adsorbed on CDS. The form of the pseudo-second order model is shown in eq. (3), where q_m (mmol g⁻¹) is the calculated value of the equilibrium adsorption quantity of ibuprofen and k_s is the pseudo-second order rate constant. q_m and k_s can be calculated from the intercept and slope by plotting t/q_t vs t . The value of q_m and k_s are listed in Table 3.

$$\frac{t}{q_t} = \frac{1}{K_s q_m^2} + \frac{t}{q_m} \quad (3)$$

The distribution coefficient³⁶ could be used to describe the inclusion ability of CDS for ibuprofen in buffer solution. The distribution coefficient (R_d) is defined by eq. (4).

$$R_d = \frac{\text{Mass of ibuprofen in adsorbant}}{\text{Mass of ibuprofen in solution}} \times \frac{v}{m_s} = \frac{q_e}{C_e} \quad (4)$$

Therefore, the distribution coefficient of ibuprofen adsorbed on CDS could be calculated and the value is 0.049 L g⁻¹. The linear correlation coefficient (R^2) which is equal to 0.997 indicates that the pseudo-second order model agrees well with inclusion adsorption of ibuprofen on CDS for the whole adsorption period. Simultaneously, q_e , which is obtained by experiment and is also listed in Table 3 is quite close to q_m . This kinetic behaviour of ibuprofen adsorbed on CDS revealed that the rate-limiting step may be chemical adsorption³⁷. This confirmed that adsorption of ibuprofen takes place via inclusion complexation until the cavities of cyclodextrin units were fully occupied.

Characterisation of unloaded and ibuprofen/CDS loaded adsorbent :

Scanning electron micrograph (SEM) analysis showed pure ibuprofen particles of cylindrical shape (Fig. 7(a)). SEM of β -CD bonded silica stationary phase (Fig. 7(b)) revealed aggregates of irregularly shaped crystals and possessed a porous structure, which should significantly in-

Table 3. Pseudo-second order model parameters for ibuprofen adsorbed on CDS with different initial concentration

Adsorbent	C_0 (mmol L ⁻¹)	K_s (g (mmol h) ⁻¹)	q_m (mmol g ⁻¹)	R^2	q_e (mmol g ⁻¹)
CDS	5	1.242	0.479	0.992	0.396
	10	0.902	0.468	0.997	0.402

C_0 is initial concentration of ibuprofen.

Fig. 7. Scanning electron micrographs for (a) CDS, (b) ibuprofen and (c) CDS after adsorption with ibuprofen.

crease the available surface area of the CDS²³. While the SEM picture of the complex (Fig. 7(c)) exhibited a totally different crystalline structure, which is not comparable with morphology of pure ibuprofen, thus suggesting formation of drug-CDS complex.

IR spectrum of CDS showed peak at 3448.09 cm^{-1} , which can be assigned to the presence of OH group. The absorption peak at 1654.58 cm^{-1} was possibly caused by the presence of the hydroxyl groups participating in an aromatic system. The changes in band positions to 3467 cm^{-1} and 1651 cm^{-1} in the IR spectrum of ibuprofen after adsorption on CDS were attributable to the formation of hydrogen bonds with CDS.

Structural features of the PM3 optimized complexes :

PM3 calculations were performed on the inclusion complexation of β -CD, HP- β -CD and S- β -CD with ibuprofen (IB). The ibuprofen molecule includes a polar COOH group, a lowly polar benzene ring, and an isobutyl "tail". The PM3 optimized structures of IB- β -CD, IB-

HP- β -CD and IB-S- β -CD are schematically illustrated in Fig. 8.

In IB- β -CD complex the acidic part of ibuprofen molecule preferred to form hydrogen bonds with the secondary hydroxyl group of β -CD rather than the primary hydroxyls. van der Waals interaction was found between the ring hydrogen atoms of the host and guest. The complex in Fig. 8(a) displayed that the benzene ring of the ibuprofen molecule was fully included into the inner hydrophobic cavity of torus shaped β -CD while the isobutyl tail exposes itself to the outside of the cavity towards the wider opening. However, in case of IB-HP- β -CD complex (Fig. 8(b)) the benzene ring also remained fully included into the CD cavity through hydrophobic and van der Waals interaction, but the acidic group directed towards the wider rim through the formation of intermolecular hydrogen bonds and isobutyl tail towards the narrower rim having van der Waals interaction with the hydrogens of the hydroxypropyl groups. Whereas in case of

Fig. 8. Optimized structures computed for complexes of ibuprofen with (a) β -CD, (b) HP- β -CD and (c) S- β -CD.

IB-S- β -CD complex (Fig.8(c)), the carboxylic acid group was included into the torus cavity of cyclodextrin through the wider rim of the S- β -CD molecule, lowly polar benzene ring was surrounded by an environment created by the sulphated sodium portion of the S- β -CD molecule and isobutyl tail remaining outside the ring. The C=O and O-H groups of the acidic part formed intermolecular hydrogen bonds with the ring hydrogens. The unexpected orientation of IB-S- β -CD complex was probably caused by the hydrophobic interaction between host and guest. The isobutyl tail of the ibuprofen showed weak van der Waal interaction with the sulphated oxygen atoms, altogether giving the most stable interaction with the S- β -CD.

The stabilization energy values of the inclusion complexes were tabulated in Table 4, which showed that S- β -CD have much stronger interaction with ibuprofen.

Table 4. Stabilization energies (ΔE) of host-guest complexes using PM3 calculations

Complex	ΔE (KJ mol ⁻¹)
IB- β -CD	-56.44
IB-HP- β -CD	-61.86
IB-S- β -CD	-136.00

Table 4 showed that the inclusion complexes are all energetically favourable, the bigger absolute values of the binding energies lead to the higher stabilities of the complexes. The binding energy values revealed that modified β -CD can form more stable complexes than β -CD itself, because modified CDs have much more interaction sites with ibuprofen and enhance the interaction between hosts and guest. The stabilization values obtained from PM3 calculation showed the same relation with the formation constant values determined by UV-Vis spectroscopy.

Conclusion :

This investigation constituted a physicochemical characterization of the interaction of β -CD and its chemically modified varieties/polymer with nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drug, ibuprofen. Spectroscopic and morphological characterizations were done in order to study the possibility of interactions between the guest and the β -CD molecules. UV-Vis and FTIR spectroscopic results demonstrated the inclusion. Molecular modeling studies cor-

roborate the experimental data showing that the results are consistent. The following conclusion can be arrived at from the above studies; (i) ibuprofen molecule forms 1 : 1 complex with CD molecules; (ii) main driving forces for inclusion were dominated by the intermolecular hydrogen bonding and hydrophobic interactions; (iii) FT-IR and SEM results suggest ibuprofen molecule formed a solid inclusion complex with CDS; (iv) stability of the inclusions increased in the following order : IB- β -CD-Hyd < IB- β -CD < IB-HP- β -CD < IB-S- β -CD; (v) S- β -CD was found to be an excellent host for inclusion with ibuprofen molecule as the stabilization energy value of its complex was more than double that obtained in case of other CD varieties and (vi) a significant blue shift had been noticed in case of IB-S- β -CD complex; (vii) the β -CD polymer functionalized on silica gel also represented a very interesting choice for inclusion with the guest molecule.

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References

1. H. Pottast, J. B. Dressman, H. E. Junginger, K. K. Midha, H. Oestr and V. P. Shah, *J. Pharm. Sci.*, 2005, **94**, 2122.
2. X. F. Kang, S. Cheley, X. Guan and H. Bayley, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2006, **128**, 10684.
3. D. Casper, U. Yaparpalvi, N. Rempel and P. Werner, *Neurosci. Lett.*, 2000, **289**, 201.
4. C. Pina-Vaz, A. G. Rodrigues, S. Costa-de-Oliveira, E. Ricardo and P. A. Mardh, *J. Antimicrob. Chemother.*, 2005, **56**, 678.
5. R. Arai, T. Sugita and A. Nishikawa, *Mycoses*, 2005, **48**, 38.
6. D. D. Chow and A. K. Karana, *Int. J. Pharm.*, 1986, **28**, 95.
7. C. Chen, F. Chen, A. Wu, H. Hsu, I. Kang and H. Cheng, *Int. J. Pharm.*, 1996, **141**, 171.
8. J. Szejtli, "Topics in Inclusion Science Cyclodextrin Technology", Dordrecht, The Netherlands, Kluwer Academic Publishers, 1988.
9. K. Uekama, F. Hirayama and T. Irie, *Chem. Rev.*, 1998, **98**, 2045.
10. T. Loftsson and M. E. Brewster, *J. Pharm. Sci.*, 1996, **85**, 1017.
11. S. Fanali, *J. Chromatogr. (A)*, 2000, **875**, 89.

12. Y. Y. Rawjee, D. U. Staerk and G. Vigh, *J. Chromatogr.*, 1993, **635**, 291.
13. P. Mura, G. P. Bettinetti, A. Manderioli, M. T. Faucci, G. Bramanti and M. Sorrenti, *Int. J. Pharm. Sci.*, 1998, **166**, 189.
14. G. R. Brown, M. R. Caira, L. R. Nassimbeni and B. Van Oudtshoorn, *J. Incl. Phenom. Mol. Recognit. Chem.*, 1996, **26**, 281.
15. A. Banik, P. Gogoi and M. D. Saikia, *J. Incl. Phenom. Macrocycl. Chem.*, 2012, **72**, 449.
16. M. D. Saikia, *Colloids Surf. (A)*, 2008, **329**, 177.
17. Y. Q. Feng, M. J. Xie and S. L. Da, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 2000, **403**, 187.
18. Y. Hu, Y. Zheng and G. Li, *Anal. Sci.*, 2004, **20**, 667.
19. M. J. Frisch, G. W. Trucks, H. B. Schlegel, G. E. Scuseria, M. A. Robb and J. R. Cheeseman, *et al.*, Gaussian 09, Revision B.01, Gaussian Inc. Wallingford CT, 2010.
20. G. Piel, G. Dive, B. Evrard, T. Van Hees, S. H. de Hassonville and L. Delattre, *Eur. J. Pharm. Sci.*, 2001, **13**, 271.
21. K. Uekama, F. Hirayama, M. Otagiri and M. Yamasaki, *Int. J. Pharm.*, 1982, **10**, 1.
22. N. Rajagopalan, S. C. Chen and W. S. Chow, *Int. J. Pharm.*, 1986, **29**, 161.
23. R. Singh, N. Bharti, J. Madan and S. N. Hiremath, *J. Pharm. Sci. Tech.*, 2010, **2**, 171.
24. E. Wernersson, J. Heyda, A. Kubickova, P. Coufal and P. Jungwirth, *J. Phys. Chem. (B)*, 2010, **114**, 11934.
25. K. Kano and H. Hasegawa, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2001, **123**, 10616.
26. H. A. Benesi and J. H. Hildebrand, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, **71**, 2703.
27. L. X. Song, H. M. Wang, P. Xu, Z. Q. Zhang and Q. Q. Liu, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 2007, **80**, 2313.
28. Y. J. Cao, X. H. Xiao, R. H. Lu and Q. X. Guo, *J. Mol. Struct.*, 2003, **660**, 73.
29. L. A. St. Pierre and K. B. Sentell, *J. Chromatogr. B : Biomed. Appl.*, 1994, **657**, 291.
30. J. Chao, J. Li, D. Meng and S. Huang, *Spectrochim. Acta, Part A*, 2003, **59**, 705.
31. S. Sajeesh and C. P. Sharma, *Int. J. Pharm.*, 2006, **325**, 147.
32. I. Bratu, A. Heranaz, J. M. Gavira and G. H. Bora, *Rom. J. Phys.*, 2005, **50**, 1063.
33. A. S. Mestre, J. Pires, J. M. F. Nogueira and A. P. Carvalho, *Carbon*, 2007, **45**, 1979.
34. M. Melillo, G. J. Phillips, J. G. Davies, A. W. Lloyd, S. R. Tennison and O. P. Kozynchenko, *Carbon*, 2004, **42**, 565.
35. F. Olak, N. Atar and A. Olgun, *Chem. Eng. J.*, 2009, **150**, 122.
36. Z. Y. Sun, M. X. Shen, A. W. Yang, C. Q. Liang, N. Wang and G. P. Cao, *Chem. Commun.*, 2011, **47**, 1072.
37. Y. S. Ho and G. McKay, *Process Biochem.*, 1999, **34**, 451.

